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On the Logic of Prime Numbers

1. Introduction

This paper outlines the underlying logic of the prime numbers. There is no attempt to prove the propositions stated in this short piece, but the reader will see that the rules that are stated are empirically verifiable as far as the reader wishes to take them, and may wish to attempt a proof of their own of these rules. No use of artificially intelligent systems has been made in the discovery or unfolding of this work. I am currently finishing a formal proof of the findings stated in this paper, together with several other topics considered of high importance to the mathematics community. I have been working on these specific projects for the past 6 years, and while my work is nearly complete, I may not be able to finalise it before similar (likely AI-boosted) discoveries are announced, which would take the sting out of my own efforts. My background is that I am a self-taught mathematician who does not currently possess a mathematics degree. I am therefore not a part of the academic mathematics community and cannot freely operate in that ecosystem. My approach to mathematics is very different to how it is ordinarily done, which I believe is the main reason for any of the successes that I have had. Why am I releasing my discovery like this? The answer to this question is threefold. First, the discovery is profound and immensely important, and needs to be shared. Secondly, artificially intelligent systems are rapidly advancing and speeding up the pace of research in mathematics. I believe that AI is now close to similar discoveries to the one announced here, and I have been frustrated at the slow pace of my formal unfolding of the discoveries (which is taking place in the context of a lengthy written work), and so I feel that while my work is nearly finished, yet now is the time to release the most substantial discovery, even if I do not provide the proof with it. Thirdly, I have been working in isolation all this time, but I am eager to connect with the wider mathematics community, and to start using AI in my researches.

What is meant by the logic of prime numbers? The most natural question will be: have I found a pattern in the prime numbers? However, I have deliberately used the term ‘logic of prime numbers’ instead of ‘pattern of prime numbers’. There is no pattern (by which I mean functional or successor relationship) that I can discern between successive prime numbers, after very considerable efforts at finding such patterns. However, there is a logic underlying how the prime numbers are arrayed in the number system. That logic is unfolded in this paper (albeit without the proof, which is in the late stages of production). The logic of prime numbers simultaneously explains why the prime numbers appear disordered (unpredictable), while having an underlying mechanism (logic) for their appearance in the number system. What follows is a result which has been extracted from a much more substantial piece of work (as yet unpublished).

2. Preliminary Definitions

Definition 1: The Sequence of Whole Numbers is that endless countable sequence which has 0 as its first object, and next after each object is the whole number next greater.¹

¹ Definition 1 here is adapted from Definition 38 of page 67 of ‘The New Elements of Mathematics’ – a posthumously published collection of mathematical writings by C.S. Peirce. See the ‘The New Elements of Mathematics’ Vol. II, by C.S. Peirce, edited by Carolyn Eisele, 1976, Mouton Publishers), p.67. Peirce’s

Definition 2: The Sequence of Positive Whole Numbers is that endless countable sequence which has 1 as its first object, and next after each object is the whole number next greater.

Definition 3: A collection of whole numbers in which no object is equal to any object except itself is called a collection of unique whole numbers, and each object of the collection is said to be a unique whole number.

Definition 4: For any two collections of unique whole numbers, the first collection is said to be a projection of the second collection if every whole number of the first collection may be connected with an equal whole number of the second collection, while every whole number of the second collection is connected with an equal whole number of the first collection. A projection is a one-to-one correspondence between the objects of the two collections of unique whole numbers, such that every object of either collection is connected with an equal object of the other collection.

Definition 5: For any two collections of unique whole numbers, the first collection is said to be a subjection of the second collection if every whole number of the first collection is equal with a whole number of the second collection, but not every whole number of the second collection is equal with a whole number of the first collection. The second collection is said to be a superjection of the first collection.

Definition 6: For any two collections of unique whole numbers, the first collection is said to be a contrajection of the second collection if no whole number of the first collection is equal with any whole number of the second collection.

Definition 7: For any two collections of unique whole numbers, the first collection is said to be an interjection of the second collection if some whole numbers of the first collection are not equal with any whole numbers of the second collection, some whole numbers of the first collection are equal with whole numbers of the second collection, some of the whole numbers of the second collection are not equal with any whole numbers of the first collection, and there exists at least one whole number which is greater than the least object of the two collections, and less than the greatest object of the two collections, but which does not belong to either collection.

Scholium 1: Definitions 4-7 are the basis for a powerful and subtle analysis of sequences. The actual analysis these definitions afford is examined in great detail in a different (as yet unpublished) work.

Definition 8: If the difference between any pair of successive objects of a sequence of whole numbers is equal to the difference between any other pair of successive objects of that sequence of whole numbers, and that difference is greater than 0, then it is called a common difference between the objects of that sequence.

terminology for a sequence such as the natural numbers (as given in the New Elements of Mathematics) is that it is a *simple sparse* sequence. I have used the term *countable* as a substitute for the terms *simple sparse*, both for brevity and because a Peircean *simple sparse* sequence maps onto the modern set-theoretic idea of a *countable* sequence. For the full definition of a simple sparse sequence as given by Peirce, see pp.36-41 of Vol. II. For the modern set-theoretic definition of a countable sequence, see 'Classic Set Theory For Guided Independent Study', Derek Goldrei, Open University, Chapman & Hall/CRC 1998, p. 143.

Definition 9: An arithmetical progression is any countable sequence of whole numbers with more than one object which has a common difference between successive objects of the sequence.

Definition 10: The First Sequence of First Object Differences is that endless arithmetical progression which has 4 as its first object and a common difference equal to 4.

Definition 11: The Second Sequence of First Object Differences is that endless arithmetical progression which has 4 as its first object and a common difference equal to 4.

Notabene: Definition 10 and Definition 11 deliberately define the same sequence under a different name.

Definition 12: The Third Sequence of First Object Differences is that endless arithmetical progression which has 10 as its first object and a common difference equal to 8.

Definition 13: The Fourth Sequence of First Object Differences is that endless arithmetical progression which has 14 as its first object and a common difference equal to 8.

Definition 14: The First Object Difference Sequence is that endless countable sequence which has the first object of the First Sequence of First Object Differences as its first object, the first object of the Second Sequence of First Object Differences as its second object, the first object of the Third Sequence of First Object Differences as its third object, the fourth object of the Fourth Sequence of First Object Differences as its fourth object, and if any object of the First Object Difference Sequence comes four objects after an object of the First Sequence of First Object Differences, then that object is equal to the object of the First Sequence of First Object Differences next greater, if any object of the First Object Difference Sequence comes four objects after an object of the Second Sequence of First Object Differences, then that object is equal to the object of the Second Sequence of First Object Differences next greater, if any object of the First Object Difference Sequence comes four objects after an object of the Third Sequence of First Object Differences, then that object is equal to the object of the Third Sequence of First Object Differences next greater, and if any object of the First Object Difference Sequence comes four objects after an object of the Fourth Sequence of First Object Differences, then that object is equal to the object of the Fourth Sequence of First Object Differences next greater.

Illustration 1: Table 1 exhibits the first ten objects of each of the sequences defined in the five preceding definitions. Notice that each object of the First Object Difference Sequence is a different object of one of the other four sequences displayed in the table.

Table 1:

First Sequence of First Object Differences	Second Sequence of First Object Differences	Third Sequence of First Object Differences	Fourth Sequence of First Object Differences	First Object Difference Sequence
4	4	10	14	4
8	8	18	22	4
12	12	26	30	10

16	16	34	38	14
20	20	42	46	8
24	24	50	54	8
28	28	58	62	18
32	32	66	70	22
36	36	74	78	12
40	40	82	86	12

Definition 15: The Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences is that endless countable sequence which has 11 as its first object, and next after any object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences is that sum which has an augend equal to the object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences which that object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences comes next after, and an addend equal to the object of the First Object Difference Sequence which corresponds with the object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences which that object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences comes next after.

Illustration 2: Table 2 exhibits the first ten objects of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences. In the table, we begin with 11, and then add the object, 4, of the First Object Difference Sequence on the same row, and the result in the object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences which comes next after (which is on the next row). That is, $11+4 = 15$.

Table 2:

First Object Difference Sequence	Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences
4	11
4	15
10	19
14	29
8	43
8	51
18	59
22	77
12	99
12	111

Definition 16: The Sequence of First Objects of Prime Number Presumption Sequences is that endless countable sequence in which any object which comes after the first object of the Sequence of First Objects of Prime Number Presumption Sequences by as many objects as that product which

has a multiplicand equal to some whole number and a multiplier equal to 2 is equal to that sum which has an augend equal to the corresponding object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences, an addend equal to the product which has a multiplicand equal to the difference which has a minuend equal to that object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences, a subtrahend equal to 5, and a multiplier equal to 2, and any object which comes after the second object of the Sequence of First Objects of Prime Number Presumption Sequences by as many objects as that product which has a multiplicand equal to some whole number and a multiplier equal to 2 is equal to that sum which has an augend equal to that product which has a multiplicand equal to the difference which has a minuend equal to that object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences, a subtrahend equal to 5, a multiplier equal to 2, and an addend equal to 2.

Illustration 3: Definition 16 defines a single sequence by applying one function to every odd numbered object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences, and a different function to every even numbered object of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences, and blending the results into a single sequence. Table 3 exhibits how the Sequence of First Objects of Prime Number Presumption Sequences is constructed by passing each value (each term or object) of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences through exactly one of the two functions, giving the output of that function as a value of the corresponding object of the Sequence of First Objects of Prime Number Presumption Sequences.

Table 3:

Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences	Calculation on each value of the Sequence of First Objects of Singular Prime Initiation Sequences	Sequence of First Objects of Prime Number Presumption Sequences
11	$11 + ((11 - 5) \times 2) = 23$	23
15	$15 + (((15 - 5) \times 2) + 2) = 37$	37
19	$19 + ((19 - 5) \times 2) = 47$	47
29	$29 + (((29 - 5) \times 2) + 2) = 79$	79
43	$43 + ((43 - 5) \times 2) = 119$	119
51	$51 + (((51 - 5) \times 2) + 2) = 145$	145
59	$59 + ((59 - 5) \times 2) = 167$	167
77	$77 + (((77 - 5) \times 2) + 2) = 223$	223
99	$99 + ((99 - 5) \times 2) = 287$	287
111	$111 + (((111 - 5) \times 2) + 2) = 325$	325
123	$123 + ((123 - 5) \times 2) = 359$	359
149	$149 + (((149 - 5) \times 2) + 2) = 439$	439
179	$179 + ((179 - 5) \times 2) = 527$	527
195	$195 + (((195 - 5) \times 2) + 2) = 577$	577
211	$211 + ((211 - 5) \times 2) = 623$	623
245	$245 + (((245 - 5) \times 2) + 2) = 727$	727
283	$283 + ((283 - 5) \times 2) = 839$	839

303	$303 + ((303 - 5) \times 2) + 2 = 901$	901
323	$323 + ((323 - 5) \times 2) = 959$	959
365	$365 + ((365 - 5) \times 2) + 2 = 1087$	1087

Definition 17: The Sequence of Odd Components of Least Addends of Succession is that endless countable sequence which has 5 as its first object, 5 as its second object, 7 as its third object, 7 as its fourth object, and any object which comes four objects after some other is equal to that sum which has an augend equal to that other, and an addend equal to 6.

Definition 18: The Sequence of Common Differences of Prime Number Presumption Sequences is that endless countable sequence which has that product which has a multiplicand equal to the first object of the Sequence of Odd Components of Least Addends of Succession, and a multiplier equal to 6, as its first object, and next after each object is equal to the product which has a multiplicand equal to the corresponding object of the Sequence of Odd Components of Least Addends of Succession, and a multiplier equal to 6.

Illustration 4: Table 4 exhibits the first ten objects of the Sequence of Odd Components of Least Addends of Succession, and the corresponding first ten objects of the Sequence of Common Differences of Prime Number Presumption Sequences.

Table 4:

Sequence of Odd Components of Least Addends of Succession	Sequence of Common Differences of Prime Number Presumption Sequences
5	$5 \times 6 = 30$
5	$5 \times 6 = 30$
7	$7 \times 6 = 42$
7	$7 \times 6 = 42$
11	$11 \times 6 = 66$
11	$11 \times 6 = 66$
13	$13 \times 6 = 78$
13	$13 \times 6 = 78$
17	$17 \times 6 = 102$
17	$17 \times 6 = 102$

Definition 19: A Prime Number Presumption Sequence is any arithmetical progression which has a first object equal to any object of the Sequence of First Objects of Prime Number Presumption Sequences, and a common difference equal to the corresponding object of the Sequence of Common Differences of Prime Number Presumption Sequences.

Illustration 5: Table 5 exhibits the constituents of the first 20 Prime Number Presumption Sequences. Each row has the first object of an arithmetical progression in the second column, and the common difference of that arithmetical progression in the third column. The two together are sufficient to define a Prime Number Presumption Sequence.

Table 5:

Sequence of Positive Whole Numbers	Sequence of First Objects of Prime Number Presumption Sequences	Sequence of Common Differences of Prime Number Presumption Sequences
1	23	30
2	37	30
3	47	42
4	79	42
5	119	66
6	145	66
7	167	78
8	223	78
9	287	102
10	325	102
11	359	114
12	439	114
13	527	138
14	577	138
15	623	150
16	727	150
17	839	174
18	901	174
19	959	186
20	1087	186

Illustration 6: The first ten terms of the first Prime Number Presumption Sequence are as follows: 23, 53, 83, 113, 143, 173, 203, 233, 263, 293...

Definition 20: A Twin Prime Number is either of two successive prime numbers which have a difference equal to 2.

Division 1: A Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence is any Prime Number Presumption Sequence which has a count equal to an odd number. A Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence is any Prime Number Presumption Sequence which has a count equal to an even number.

Scholium 2: Every row of Table 5 which has an odd number in the first column has the first object of the corresponding Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence in the second column of that row, and the corresponding common difference of that Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence in the third column of that row; and every row of Table 5 which has an even number in the first column has the first object of the corresponding Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence in the second column of that row, and the corresponding common difference of that Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence in the third column of that row.

Illustration 7: Every other row of Table 5, beginning with the *first* row of Table 5, defines a Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence. For example, the arithmetical progression which has a first object equal to 47 and a common difference equal to 42 is a Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence, because its constituents come some multiple of 2 rows after the first row. Every other row of Table 5, beginning with the *second* row of Table 5, defines a Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence. For example, the arithmetical progression which has a first object equal to 223 and a common difference equal to 78 is a Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence, because its constituents come some multiple of 2 rows after the second row.

3. Prime Candidate Array

Proposition 1: 2 and 3 are prime numbers.

Proposition 2: 2 and 3 are the only prime numbers which have a difference equal to 1.

Definition 21: The Prime Candidate Array is that array which is constructed by the following rules:

- 1) The first row of the first column of the array has in it the number 0, and next after each row of the first column is the number 4 greater than the number in the row of that column which that row comes next after.
- 2) The first row of the second column of the array has in it the number 2, and next after each row of the second column is the number 4 greater than the number in the row of that column which that row comes next after.
- 3) The first row of the third column of the array has in it the number 5, and next after each row of the third column is the number 2 greater than the number in the row of that column which that row comes next after.
- 4) Each row of the fourth column has in it the sum which has an augend equal to the object of the first column on the same row, and an addend equal to the object of the third column on the same row, and also the sum which has an augend equal to the object of the second column on the same row, and an addend equal to the object of the third column on the same row. Note that it will be obvious to any mathematician that every prime number greater than 3 exists in the fourth column.

Illustration 8: Table 6 exhibits the first 150 rows of the Prime Candidate Array. Each pair of numbers in the candidate column is obtained by adding, first the number in a row of column 1 to the number on the same row of column 3, and second the number in the same row of column 2 to the number on the same row of column 3. For example. $8+9 = 17$, and $10+9 = 19$, and 17 19 is the pair of prime candidates on the fourth row of the table (with the header row being the first row of the table).

Table 6:

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	CANDIDATES
0	2	5	5 7
4	6	7	11 13
8	10	9	17 19
12	14	11	23 25
16	18	13	29 31
20	22	15	35 37
24	26	17	41 43
28	30	19	47 49

32	34	21	53 55
36	38	23	59 61
40	42	25	65 67
44	46	27	71 73
48	50	29	77 79
52	54	31	83 85
56	58	33	89 91
60	62	35	95 97
64	66	37	101 103
68	70	39	107 109
72	74	41	113 115
76	78	43	119 121
80	82	45	125 127
84	86	47	131 133
88	90	49	137 139
92	94	51	143 145
96	98	53	149 151
100	102	55	155 157
104	106	57	161 163
108	110	59	167 169
112	114	61	173 175
116	118	63	179 181
120	122	65	185 187
124	126	67	191 193
128	130	69	197 199
132	134	71	203 205
136	138	73	209 211
140	142	75	215 217
144	146	77	221 223
148	150	79	227 229
152	154	81	233 235
156	158	83	239 241
160	162	85	245 247
164	166	87	251 253
168	170	89	257 259
172	174	91	263 265
176	178	93	269 271
180	182	95	275 277
184	186	97	281 283
188	190	99	287 289
192	194	101	293 295
196	198	103	299 301

4. Prime Number Array

Scholium 3: Every prime number in the array we are about to construct has an non-arbitrary or natural identity which is derived from the relationship between the numbers in the CANDIDATES column and the Prime Number Presumption Sequences which we defined in the second section.

This is different than a sieve method. It specifies the exact relationships which define primality. That is, the Prime Number Array is a specification of the mechanics which *determine* the prime numbers. As we shall see, the prime numbers are not “randomly” distributed, but are not patterned either. Prime Numbers are therefore difficult to predict but mechanistically (that is, logically) determined by the rules of the Prime Number Array.

Proposition 3: Any two different Prime Number Presumption Sequences which have *equal* common differences are contrajections of each other.

Proposition 4: Any two different Prime Number Presumption Sequences which have *different* common differences are interjections of each other.

Scholium 4: As mentioned, the proofs of any propositions in this paper are left to another piece of work.

Definition 22: A Singular Prime Number is any prime number which either only belongs to some whole number, greater than 0, of Two Prime Number Presumption Sequences, or which only belongs to some whole number, greater than 0, of Four Prime Number Presumption Sequences, but does not belong at once to a Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence and a Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence.

Definition 23: The Prime Number Array is that array which is constructed by the following rules:

- 1) The Prime Candidate Array is constructed according to Definition 21.
- 2) If a number in the CANDIDATE column belongs to any number of Prime Number Presumption Sequences, such that either every one of those Prime Number Presumption Sequences is a Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence, or every one of those Prime Number Presumption Sequences is a Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence, then that number is a Singular Prime Number.
- 3) If a number of the CANDIDATE column belongs to any number of Prime Number Presumption Sequences, such that at least one of those Prime Number Presumption Sequences is a Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence, and at least one of those Prime Number Presumption Sequences is a Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence, then that number is a Composite Number.
- 4) If a number of the CANDIDATE column does not belong to any Prime Number Presumption Sequence, then that number is one of a pair of Twin Prime Numbers.

Illustration 8: Table 7 exhibits the beginning of the first ten Prime Number Presumption Sequences in Columns 7 to 15. We see that the first three rows of Column 6 have three sets of Twin Prime Numbers in them, because there is no object of any Prime Number Presumption Sequence (in Columns 7 through 15) on any of those rows. They are therefore Twin Primes by default. Rows labelled 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 are examples of Singular Prime Numbers (Prime Numbers which are non-Twin Primes), because each number belongs only to either Two Prime Number Presumption Sequences or Four Twin Prime Number Presumption Sequences (but not both). On the row labelled 29 we see an example of a Singular Prime Number which belongs to more than one Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence, but does not belong to any Four Prime Number Presumption Sequence. Since it belongs only to Two Singular Prime Number Presumption Sequences, then it is a Singular Prime Number. Again, looking at the row labelled 24, we have the numbers 143 and 145, such that 143 belongs to a Two Prime Number Presumption Sequence, while 145 belongs to a Four

Prime Number Presumption Sequence. Therefore, both 143 and 145 are composite numbers, by Definition 23.

Table 7:

ROW	A	B	C	CANDIDATES	PRIMES	2	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	2
1	0	2	5	5 7	5 7									
2	4	6	7	11 13	11 13									
3	8	10	9	17 19	17 19									
4	12	14	11	23 25	23	23								
5	16	18	13	29 31	29 31									
6	20	22	15	35 37	37		37							
7	24	26	17	41 43	41 43									
8	28	30	19	47 49	47			47						
9	32	34	21	53 55	53	53								
10	36	38	23	59 61	59 61									
11	40	42	25	65 67	67		67							
12	44	46	27	71 73	71 73									
13	48	50	29	77 79	79				79					
14	52	54	31	83 85	83	83								
15	56	58	33	89 91	89			89						
16	60	62	35	95 97	97		97							
17	64	66	37	101 103	101 103									
18	68	70	39	107 109	107 109									
19	72	74	41	113 115	113	113								
20	76	78	43	119 121					121	119				
21	80	82	45	125 127	127		127							
22	84	86	47	131 133	131			131						
23	88	90	49	137 139	137 139									
24	92	94	51	143 145		143					145			
25	96	98	53	149 151	149 151									
26	100	102	55	155 157	157		157							
27	104	106	57	161 163	163				163					
28	108	110	59	167 169	167							167		
29	112	114	61	173 175	173	173		173						
30	116	118	63	179 181	179 181									
31	120	122	65	185 187			187			185				
32	124	126	67	191 193	191 193									
33	128	130	69	197 199	197 199									
34	132	134	71	203 205		203			205					
35	136	138	73	209 211	211						211			
36	140	142	75	215 217			217	215						
37	144	146	77	221 223	223								223	
38	148	150	79	227 229	227 229									
39	152	154	81	233 235	233	233								
40	156	158	83	239 241	239 241									
41	160	162	85	245 247			247		247			245		
42	164	166	87	251 253	251					251				
43	168	170	89	257 259	257			257						

44	172	174	91	263 265	263	263											
45	176	178	93	269 271	269	271											
46	180	182	95	275 277	277		277					277					
47	184	186	97	281 283	281	283											
48	188	190	99	287 289						289							287
49	192	194	101	293 295	293	293											
50	196	198	103	299 301					299								301

5. Conclusions

The mystery of prime numbers is solved by this analysis. Prime numbers are not “randomly” distributed throughout the number system (unless we are to define randomness using this analysis), and they are also not patterned (if by a pattern among any set of primes we mean some kind of successor relation which obtains between the primes of that set), but instead they are determined by the relationships between Prime Number Presumption Sequences and the sequence of Candidates. Those relationships are defined by the rules of Definition 23. We have stated the rules for deriving every Prime Number Presumption Sequence in the second section. Every number of a Prime Number Presumption Sequence may be presumed to be a Singular Prime Number unless its counterpart in the sequence of Candidates belongs to some Prime Number Presumption Sequence of a different kind, as described in Definition 23, in which case it is a composite number. Those Candidates which are not Singular Prime Numbers (that is, do not belong to some Prime Number Presumption Sequence), are all Twin Prime Numbers by default. This analysis exactly determines the identity of prime numbers. Questions abound at this point. We conclude by stating just one interesting conjecture relating to this discovery which may help in finding large prime numbers.

Conjecture: There exists at least one pair of Twin Prime Numbers which comes after the first object of some Prime Number Presumption Sequence, and which comes before the first object of the Prime Number Presumption Sequence which comes next after.